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On the Cognitive, Metacognitive, and Agentic Effects of Creativity Training

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Abstract

This article examines the mechanisms by which creativity training enhances creative abilities and confidence. An extensive creativity training program (5 months of weekly training for almost seven hundred participants aged 10-17, assigned to the intervention and control group) was used to examine two alternative hypotheses. The first predicted that the increase in creative confidence due to training is mediated by the rise in creative abilities: the *abilities-shape-confidence-effect*. An alternative hypothesis posited that the increase in creative abilities due to training is mediated by the rise in creative confidence: the *to-believe-is-to-rise effect*. Although both these effects occurred, the change in participants' creative abilities fully mediated their growth in creative confidence. This pattern suggests metacognitive mechanisms through which creativity training works. We discuss the theoretical and practical implications of those results and provide recommendations for creativity training.

Keywords: creativity training; creative agency; creative metacognition; creative abilities; the abilities-shape-confidence-effect

On the Cognitive, Metacognitive, and Agentic Effects of Creativity Training

Creativity training is an effective way of stimulating the potential of children, adolescents, and adults (McKay et al., 2024; Scott et al., 2004a). Although recent meta-analyses suggest that its effects might have been overestimated due to the publication bias and the large number of underpowered studies (Karwowski et al., 2022; Sio & Lortie-Forgues, 2024), it seems safe to claim that scholars and practitioners alike do have a variety of options to enrich and strengthen the creative potential of themselves and their students. Indeed, and quite fortunately, there are several ways of enhancing creativity (Haase et al., 2023; Scott et al., 2004b; Valgeirsdottir & Onarheim, 2017).

Initiated by the Osborn-Parnes creative problem-solving process, the idea of stimulating creativity through teaching problem-solving steps and techniques has been used in dozens, if not hundreds, of interventions. Consequently, there is empirical evidence for the effectiveness of using both multi-method programs (cf. Ma, 2006) as well as particular techniques focusing on select creativity-relevant processes, like SCAMPER (Poon et al., 2014), brainstorming (Puccio et al., 2020), TRIZ (Park, 2023), or six thinking hats (Hu et al., 2021). Similarly, recent decades witnessed a richness of training approaches, from training inspired by neuroscience (Onarheim & Friis-Olivarius, 2013), to those specific to STEM (Aguilera & Ortiz-Revilla, 2021), or design thinking (Liu et al., 2024), all the way to educational robotics (Zhang & Zhu, 2022), drama (Celume et al., 2019), virtual reality (Wang et al., 2024), or role-playing (Karwowski & Soszynski, 2008).

The effectiveness of creativity training has been tested across various contexts, including organizations (McKay et al., 2024), public service teams (Tan et al., 2023), the military (Fletcher & Benveniste, 2022), and school settings (Ruiz-del-Pino et al., 2022). Moreover, creativity has been supported as a subject in academic courses (Puccio et al., 2020), an element of school problem-solving pedagogy (Zhan et al., 2024), and in international problem-solving competitions (Spoon et al., 2021). The complex nature of creativity implies different types of creativity training related to the domains of creative activities (Baer, 2016). Indeed, while some interventions focus on creative

writing (Graham et al., 2012), others are primarily visual art-focused (Hoffman et al., 2021) or stimulate creativity in dance (Richards et al., 2024), improvisational theater (West et al., 2017), engineering (Bourgeois-Bougrine et al., 2017), or creative business modeling (Lund et al., 2017).

Despite this richness of approaches, and somehow ironically, we know little about the mechanisms through which creativity training works. Consider, for example, the extent to which its effects transfer across domains (Baer, 2016; Fink et al., 2020) or inform noncognitive characteristics of the participants, for example, their creative self-efficacy (Byrge & Tang, 2015; Meinel et al., 2019; Vally et al., 2019) or creative self-concept (Poon et al., 2014; Zielińska et al., 2022b). How exactly does this improvement happen? Pop-psychological bestsellers would argue that creativity is developed in a manner akin to muscles in sports training. Such a metaphor, however, explains close to nothing.

A promising but overlooked direction of searching for plausible mechanisms is testing whether training works through the motivational and metacognitive lens. Such a metacognitive argument was posited some time ago (Pesut, 1990), but it was largely overlooked. Yet it seems likely that training works not only because some specific skills are exercised and abilities developed but also because participants come to understand what creativity is and why it matters. People's implicit theories of creativity may have profound regulatory consequences, including their self-perception and recognition of creativity in others, such as students or collaborators (Gralewski & Karwowski, 2018; Sternberg, 1985). Consequently, those who start to consider themselves more creative or change their perception of creativity might feel encouraged to engage in creative activities more often and intensively (Zielińska et al., 2022b). Furthermore, this suggests that metacognitive and motivational mechanisms, such as raising awareness and knowledge about creativity, may also be important in strengthening abilities and skills. This mechanism would indicate a kind of *to-believe-is-to-rise effect*, i.e., an expectation that participants' conviction about the value of creativity and their creative potential leads to more pronounced effects of the training.

This paper explores the cognitive, metacognitive, and agentic consequences of creativity training. Specifically, we inquire whether developing creative skills due to training might be responsible for improving participants' self-perception as more creative. Hence, we are interested in the transfer of training effects from cognitive (an increase in creative abilities) to agentic (an increase in creative confidence), a transfer that may occur thanks to participants' metacognitive awareness (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023), i.e., the recognition that their creative skills have improved. The perspective we take in this paper focuses on the so-called mini-c and little-c creativity (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2009), e.g., relatively domain-general aspects of creative thought and action (Plucker & Beghetto, 2004). The same applies to creative confidence – as we explain below, we are mostly interested in the domain-general aspects of creative self-perception rather than specific, e.g., art- or science-related self-beliefs.

Creativity as Agentic Action: Theoretical Background

Recent developments in the creativity literature have explored the agentic underpinnings of creative action quite intensively. Following a metaphor coined two decades ago (Sternberg, 2002), creativity is seen as an activity driven by a decision to behave in a certain way and defy the crowd if needed. Because such decisions are risky, most people avoid exploring unknown paths and opt for safer solutions (Beghetto et al., 2020). Thus, the lack of creative attempts might not necessarily be caused by the lack of creative abilities; the reason for creative underachievement may lie in the absence of perceived or exercised agency.

The Creative Behavior as Agentic Action (CBAA) model (Beghetto & Karwowski, in press; Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019) proposes a dynamic interrelation of cognitive (creative potential, e.g., divergent thinking) and agentic (personality-related and motivational) factors. The initial incarnation of this model primarily focused on two elements perceived as focal for creative agency. The first is *creative confidence*—the term used here to avoid problems associated with previously applied labels, mainly creative self-concept and creative self-efficacy (see also Zandi et al., 2022)—which refers to individuals' beliefs that they can approach problems in a new and effective way. Previous works

operationalized creative confidence as either a stable, trait-like creative self-concept or more dynamic, situation-specific, state-like creative self-efficacy (Beghetto & Karwowski, 2017a). Indeed, creative confidence can have either a more domain-general or domain-specific face depending on the theoretical perspective and the measurement applied. Notably, although relatively stable (Zandi et al., 2022), it could also be improved (Zielińska & Karwowski, in press).

The second focal factor in the CBAA model is *creative centrality*. Again, this term is used in this paper to avoid misunderstandings associated with previously used labels, mainly creative personal identity and valuing creativity (Zandi et al., 2022; Zielińska et al., 2022a). Centrality refers to the importance of creativity to an individual; the value that being creative holds for them. Hence, centrality is an identity-related factor. While creative confidence describes the “I can (be creative)” perspective, creative centrality is more “I am” or “I want to be (creative)” conviction.

The revised CBAA model (Beghetto & Karwowski, in press) pays special attention to two additional agentic elements that work hand in hand with confidence and centrality. The first is risk-taking, i.e., the tendency to deal with uncertainty and engage in unknown behaviors. The second is self-regulation, which refers to the ability to plan, monitor, and manage creative actions (Zielińska et al., 2023). Given that the study presented below focuses primarily on creative confidence, we do not delve deeper into discussing risk-taking and self-regulation, which are described in detail elsewhere (Beghetto & Karwowski, in press; Zielińska & Karwowski, 2022; Zielińska et al., 2024).

The CBAA model posits that creative confidence serves as a mediator in the relationship between creative potential and action that leads to new and valuable outcomes. The logic of this mediational path stems from the tenets of the sociocognitive theory (Bandura, 1997) and some recent theoretical developments in the creativity literature.

According to sociocognitive theorizing, there are at least four distinct mechanisms that may contribute to making people with higher creative potential also more confident in their creativity. The first mechanism is experiential and involves mastery experiences. As Bandura (1997) explains, mastery experiences is a key factor driving people’s self-efficacy. If someone has succeeded in solving

creative problems in the past, they are likely to consider themselves creative. The second factor is social persuasion. It stems from verbal and non-verbal feedback received from teachers, parents, supervisors, or friends. Given that creative people have more opportunities to receive such positive reinforcement, it forms a crucial building block of their confidence (but see Mueller et al., 2012). Next, so-called vicarious experiences, primarily associated with social modeling, come into play. Observing creative people at work allows one to understand the nuances of creative action and form “I can” conviction. And here again, creative people might have more opportunities to observe such role models (Huang et al., 2016; Simonton, 1984). The fourth and final mechanism involves physiological and affective states (Bandura, 1997). Creativity enhances positive affect and predicts greater willpower (Henderson et al., 2023), which in turn can increase confidence when facing creative challenges and strengthen one’s belief in personal efficacy.

In addition to the four sources of self-efficacy identified by Bandura (see also Benedek et al., 2025), the link between creative potential and confidence hypothesized by the CBAA model may also be driven by people’s metacognition. Creative individuals typically recognize their own creativity (Silvia, 2008), even if they occasionally underestimate their potential (Sidi et al., 2020; Urban & Urban, 2021). Metacognitive accuracy (Karwowski et al., 2020; Lebuda & Benedek, 2023): being aware of someone’s actual creativity may strengthen the association between a person’s potential and their self-perception.

Overall, although there are quite specific mechanisms through which creative potential might influence creative confidence, exact empirical tests of this proposed causal link are challenging. Complex longitudinal designs illustrating that a path from potential to confidence is not only correlational but also causal and remains statistically significant when the reciprocity of the potential-confidence relationship is considered would be particularly appropriate here, yet are missing. Experimental testing of this reasoning is even more problematic, as it requires manipulating creative potential, for example, by enhancing someone’s creative abilities and then analyzing

whether and to what extent this improvement is associated with increased confidence. This paper focuses on this latter solution by attempting to test the CBAA-derived hypothesis experimentally.

To date, the main prepositions of the CBAA model have been primarily tested in cross-sectional and longitudinal studies (e.g., Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019; see also Beghetto & Karwowski, in press, for an overview), although some daily diary interventions explore select CBAA assumptions (Zielińska & Karwowski, in press). What seems well-corroborated is the moderating effect of creative centrality in the association between potential and performance. Indeed, across studies, creative centrality qualified the strength of the link between people's potential and activity (and—consequently—their achievement). What requires more tests is the hypothesized mediation of confidence in the relationship between potential and behavior. Remarkably, this proposed *abilities-shape-confidence-effect* (ASCE) is yet to be tested.

In this paper, we offer a novel way to test this prediction. Our reasoning is as follows. Suppose the assumptions of the CBAA model are sound, and creative potential causally influences creative confidence. We posit that such a hypothesis might be tested, drawing upon the opportunities created in empirical studies on the effectiveness of creativity training. Previous studies and meta-analyses have provided compelling evidence that creativity training enhances creative abilities (Scott et al., 2004a), both in children (Alves-Oliveira et al., 2021) and adults (Haase et al., 2023; Tsai, 2014). Thus, in a sense, the training allows researchers “to manipulate” participants' creative abilities by assigning them to an intervention or control group. If the change in abilities caused by the intervention also alters people's creative confidence, such a pattern would be consistent with the CBAA logic and demonstrate agentic and metacognitive transfer. In such a hypothetical scenario, participants' confidence grows *due to* the growth in their creative abilities. Therefore, more technically speaking, the ASCE occurs in a design with experimental and control groups that take pretest and posttest measurements of abilities and confidence, assuming that the change in confidence resulting from *the training is mediated by the change in abilities*. But suppose there is a significant improvement in creative abilities in the intervention group (vs. the control

group), but no improvement in creative confidence.¹ The CBAA predictions cannot be met in this scenario, so ASCE must be rejected.

Thus, the reasoning tested in this paper requires two effects to co-occur. The first requirement is that creativity training improves creative abilities and confidence. Given the focus of typical creativity training, we do not deem it necessary that improvement in creative abilities and confidence is comparable in terms of the effect size. Quite the opposite, we expect more substantial effects on abilities than on confidence; however, if only abilities improve without a corresponding increase in confidence, the first requirement is not met. The second requirement addresses the precise mechanism of the change. If the ASCE assumption is sound, the improvement in creative confidence thanks to the training (i.e., the difference between the pretest and posttest in the intervention group compared to the same difference in the control group) should be mediated by a change in abilities. This would allow us to conclude that people became more creatively confident after the training *because* their creative abilities improved.

However, another theoretically plausible hypothesis can also suggest some metacognitive and motivational effects of the training. If the impact of creativity training on participants' abilities (i.e., the improvement in the intervention group) occurs via a change in their confidence, another mechanism seems to be in place, one that suggests this is the confidence that allows abilities to grow rather than vice versa: the *to-believe-is-to-rise effect*. In the following study, we test both of these alternative mechanisms. First, however, we briefly discuss how and why creativity training works.

How Does Creativity Training Work?

¹ Notably, a scenario that is both possible and interesting to consider is one in which creative potential increases, yet confidence not only does not increase, but declines. Although surprising at first sight, it is entirely reasonable for several reasons. Although more creative people are usually quite aware of their potential, people in general tend to overestimate their skills (Zell et al., 2019). Along these lines, two recent studies demonstrated that people benefited from feedback associated with their creative performance and improved creatively, yet at the same time, their self-assessments in subsequent tasks decreased. Importantly, this decrease resulted in more accurate self-perception, i.e., higher correlations between self-assessment and objective creativity scores. Hence, although self-perception declined, while performance improved, the correlation between the two grew: people became better calibrated in their self-assessment (de Chantal et al., 2025).

As we already mentioned, usually studies examining the effectiveness of creativity training concentrate on the cognitive aspects of participants' functioning (Alves-Oliveira et al., 2021; Scott et al., 2004a, 2004b; Valgeirsdottir & Onarheim, 2017), and so far, the highest effectiveness has been shown for divergent thinking or problem-solving skills (Scott et al., 2004a; Tsai, 2014). Much less attention in the research on creativity training has been paid to self-regulation (Karwowski et al., 2022; Zielińska et al., 2022b) and metacognition, including its more dynamic aspects, such as monitoring and control, and more stable metacognitive knowledge (Antonietti et al., 2021; Hargrove & Nietfeld, 2015; May et al., 2020). Consequently, we know relatively little about the effects of creativity training on the development of self-regulatory and metacognitive processes and strategies.

Similarly, although some recent works show that creativity training and wise interventions (Zielińska et al., 2022b) strengthen people's creative confidence and centrality, such studies are also scarce. It seems likely, however, that even creativity training that primarily focuses on developing participants' creative abilities can enhance their metacognition and agency. Why would such a beneficial "side effect" occur? We expect that the previously discussed sources of self-efficacy, as presented in sociocognitive theorizing (Bandura, 1997), as well as some metacognitive mechanisms, may also be at play here.

First, given that the creative process involves a constant iteration between idea generation and evaluation/selection (Kleinmintz et al., 2019), it engages cognitive and metacognitive components (Puente-Díaz et al., 2021). Creative abilities and evaluation skills are positively correlated (Guo et al., 2022; de Chantal et al., 2024; Karwowski et al., 2020), and metacognition has recently been demonstrated to serve as a necessary condition for effective idea generation (Urban & Urban, 2023). Creativity training offers several opportunities to activate metacognitive processes, such as making social comparisons (cf. Michinov et al., 2015; Li et al., 2023; Richter et al., 2012) and perspective-taking, for example, through continuous role-switching between author and observer. These aspects are likely to prompt participants to think about their potential. Furthermore, noticing the increased creative potential might impact how participants evaluate their ideas and themselves

more generally. In short, it seems likely, even if direct evidence is lacking, that creativity training can enrich metacognitive knowledge, which is vital for creativity (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023).

Second, as already discussed, mastery experiences drive creative self-efficacy (Dampérat et al., 2016; Mathisen & Bronnick, 2009). Creativity training provides opportunities to experience small, personal successes while performing tasks or presenting results. Successes perceived by the individual and reinforced by the group provide participants with knowledge of their abilities, shape self-confidence, and drive motivation to continue the activity in the future.

Third, drawing accurate conclusions about one's potential is easier when participants in creativity training can systematically observe themselves and others and deliberate on their progress. More creative peers in the classroom or training group might reinforce the individual's creative self-concept (Karwowski, 2015a). This is not only a matter of comparison but also modeling (Groenendijk et al., 2013), given that vicarious experiences also shape creative self-efficacy (Dampérat et al., 2016). The role of peers is particularly vital for adolescents (Anderson & Haney, 2021), while for the youngest training participants, it is teachers or trainers who serve as role models (Soh, 2017).

Fourth and finally, feedback is vital to creativity (de Chantal et al., 2025; Redifer et al., 2021) and may enhance the training effects (Maltzmann et al., 1958). Metacognitive monitoring activated by feedback leads to higher originality (de Chantal & Organisciak, 2023; de Chantal et al., 2024; 2025). In creativity training, other participants offer feedback, making it easier to develop and improve the ideas presented (De Stobbeleir et al., 2011). Through peer-to-peer feedback, students' creative confidence can more accurately reflect their actual creative performance (Liu et al., 2016). Therefore, it seems reasonable to expect creativity training to enhance the metacognitive and agentic aspects of creativity, even if this is not its primary focus.

The Present Study

To test the theoretical reasoning outlined above, we took advantage of the opportunity presented by a large and extensive creativity training program (Wiśniewska, 2021). As we explain in more detail in our Procedure section, the training was conducted over five months, with weekly classes, in a pre-

post intervention and control group design. We acknowledge that although this research program was initially planned to examine only some basic yet cardinal research questions—i.e., does the training work in improving participants' creativity?—it has also created a space to test the hypotheses outlined below.

Our primary hypothesis expects the ASCE: *abilities-shape-confidence effect*. It is examined in two steps. First, we assess whether the training has improved participants' creative potential and their creative confidence. Thus, we hypothesize that the training will have positive effects on both creative abilities and creative confidence. However, based on the training content described below, we expect more substantial effects on abilities than on confidence. Our second step is a formal test of the ASCE. As already explained, what is deemed necessary is to demonstrate that a change in confidence (i.e., expected growth) might be attributed to the change in abilities. We test this logic in a mediation model, regressing posttest scores in creative confidence on a group variable ($0 = control$, $1 = experimental$) and posttest scores in creative abilities while controlling for pretest scores in creative confidence and abilities (see Hayes, 2015, pp. 568-572 for a discussion of this approach). We estimate the indirect effect, "training–change in abilities–change in confidence," to formally test our reasoning. Examining the alternative hypothesis, we also check whether the improvement in abilities resulting from the training can be attributed to the change in confidence: the *to-believe-is-to-rise effect*. This study was not preregistered.

Method

Participants

There were 674 participants aged 10-17 ($M = 12.91$, $SD = 2.32$) assigned to either an intervention group ($n = 301$) or a control group ($n = 373$). The overall sample consisted of 364 girls (54%) and 310 boys (46%), with ages ranging from 10 to 17 years ($M = 13.30$, $SD = 2.19$). Participants in the intervention were assigned to 23 age-matched groups, with each group consisting of an average of 14 participants. Intervention and control groups were age-matched (intervention: $M = 13.27$, $SD = 2.29$, control: $M = 13.32$, $SD = 2.11$, $t[672] = -0.306$, $p = .760$).

Measures

Creative Potential. Creative abilities were assessed in group settings, using two performance paper-and-pencil tests administered without time limits in a pretest and posttest design. The first instrument applied was the figural Test of Creative Thinking Drawing Production (TCT-DP), Form A (Jellen & Urban, 1986). The second measure was the Test of Creative Imagery (TCI) (Karwowski, 2008a, 2008b; see also Karwowski & Soszynski, 2008; McKay et al., 2017), an instrument that combines figural and verbal modalities.

In TCT-DP, participants complete an unfinished drawing with several initial elements. The scoring is based on fourteen criteria, most of which are formal (i.e., objective), resulting in a total score. Scoring of TCT-DP was conducted by three trained research assistants who had completed a course that made them familiar with the assessment criteria. Coders were unaware whether they were scoring pretest or posttest, or the intervention or control group test sheets. Each coder scored a random one-third of all test sheets; thus, each test was scored by only one coder. The overall TCT-DP score, composed of fourteen criteria, was reliable at both the pretest ($\alpha = .74$) and posttest ($\alpha = .78$). As additional evidence of reliability, we used the test-retest (pretest-posttest) correlation between the total scores in the control group, which was high, $r = .817$ ($p < .001$), an equivalent of Cronbach's $\alpha = .90$.

The next test used, TCI, requires participants to produce original yet straightforward drawings that represent something that does not exist, but—according to the participant—should exist. Participants are provided with 16 initial elements (four straight lines, four dots, four curvy lines, and four semicircles) (see Fig. 1 for elements and example drawings). After finishing, each participant provides a title or a brief description of their drawings. TCI was scored by the same three trained coders who scored TCT-DP. Scoring involved fluency (the number of drawings created, thus assessed entirely objectively), flexibility (the number of categories into which the drawings could be classified), and originality, which was scored according to the provided rubric. Again, each test was scored by a single coder, and all tests were randomly distributed across coders. Before scoring, coders

participated in pre-coding training sessions. As evidence for TCI reliability in our study, we used test-retest (pretest-posttest) correlations in the control group, which were $r = .45, p < .001$ ($\alpha = .62$) for fluency, $r = .40, p < .001$ ($\alpha = .57$) for flexibility, and $r = .72, p < .001$ ($\alpha = .84$) for originality. The total score of the TCI (aggregated across fluency, flexibility, and originality) in the control group was highly correlated at the pretest and posttest measurements, $r = .57, p < .001, \alpha = .73$.

Figure 1. TCI initial elements and examples of participants' drawing and descriptions (titles)

provided

To facilitate reporting our results, we created an overall factor of creative abilities standardized and then averaged across the TCT-DP and TCI scales. We scale the variable so that the results of the pretest have an $M = 100$ and $SD = 15$, so we transformed the creative potential index to an IQ scale. Such an index was reliable in both the pretest ($\alpha = .75$) and posttest ($\alpha = .83$). Given that the specific findings for each test precisely mirrored the results presented below, we decided to focus on a more general picture. The detailed results regarding both tests (and scales within TCI) are provided in the study's OSF archive (see the annotated JASP file in the OSF).

Creative Confidence. Creative confidence was measured twice using a single-item question: "How creative do you consider yourself?" with a 5-point Likert scale ($1 = \textit{definitely not creative}$, $5 =$

very creative). Overall, the scale was slightly skewed toward higher scores, with pretest $M = 3.85$; $SD = 0.79$, and posttest $M = 3.93$; $SD = 0.82$, yet the values of both skewness (pretest = -0.308 , posttest = -0.48) and kurtosis (pretest = 0.02 , posttest = 0.14) have shown it was appropriate for multivariate analyses. The reliability of a single-item measurement estimated as the test-retest correlation in the control group was good, $r = .626$, $p < .001$ ($\alpha = .77$).

Procedure

The assessment was conducted using a paper-and-pencil format and administered in a group setting in schools. Each participant was assigned a unique code that was used to label their test sheets. Both measurements employed the same research instruments.

Participants in the intervention group attended training sessions once a week for five months, each lasting approximately two hours. Creativity training was implemented as an extracurricular activity in 15 schools across a medium-sized town in central Poland. Participation was open to all children in these schools, but only those whose parents provided written consent and confirmed availability (i.e., the timing of the classes did not overlap with other school obligations, as outlined in the school timetables) were considered for participation. The control group consisted of randomly selected children from the same schools and nearby. The control group did not participate in the intervention, but attended regular school classes. Additional survey questions allowed for the exclusion of students who simultaneously attended other creative classes (thus isolating the effect of the independent variable), although such cases were marginal.

Intervention

The key cognitive component in our model of creativity training (see Figure 2) is creative abilities, understood as cognitive predispositions enabling the production of new, original, yet valuable ideas and solutions to problems (Runco & Jaeger, 2012). The main elements of creative abilities addressed in training were divergent thinking (Runco & Acar, 2012), creative imagination, and imagery (Glăveanu et al., 2017; cf. LeBoutillier & Marks, 2003). The intervention also addressed other mental operations engaged during the creative thinking process. Based on the literature review

(e.g., Finke et al., 1992; Lassig, 2013; Pinkow, 2023; van de Kamp et al., 2016; Welling, 2007), the training focused on combining, transforming, making associations, abstracting, metaphorizing, and anticipating. Given that the creative process usually relies heavily on combinatory skills and exploring unknown combinations of known ideas (Boden, 2003; Finke et al., 1992), particular attention was paid to providing a space for these mechanisms in training.

Figure 2. Theoretical model of creativity training

Although the training primarily focused on the cognitive aspects of creativity, it did not ignore emotional and personality factors relevant to creative functioning. Two that received particular attention were openness to experience and curiosity/wonder. It is well-established that openness to experience is a personality trait of particular importance for creativity (Chen et al., 2023; Lebuda et al., 2021; Puryear et al., 2017). Individuals high in openness are characterized by neophilia, higher aesthetic sensitivity, a tendency to evaluate new experiences positively, and an ease in assimilating novel information. Openness is also reflected in the search for knowledge in various fields, which closely relates to various topics covered in the creativity training, including nature, art, language, and

media. Curiosity is a central component of openness (Silvia & Christensen, 2020), robustly related to creativity (Schutte & Malouff, 2020). It denotes the desire to learn and discover new and unobvious phenomena, a kind of awareness of what can happen at a given moment (Kashdan & Silvia, 2009). One of the goals of the training conducted was to cultivate curiosity as a key feature, referred to as “being curious” or “feeling curiosity” (see Karwowski & Zielińska, 2024). This experience was accompanied by a sense of wonder, defined through interrelated processes: awareness, excitement, and exploration (Glăveanu, 2019; Glăveanu et al., 2024), as well as awe (Chirico et al., 2018). The social context of group and individual learning is also emphasized (Korde & Paulus, 2017; Shin & Jang, 2015).

The training program was implemented in 12 thematic blocks. The selected topics aimed to embed the tasks in the participants’ reality, encompassing their everyday problems, whether culture-related, historical threads, or environmental concerns. The titles of classes, their objectives, and excerpts from the introductions to the scenarios are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Topics of individual creativity training classes

Session 1: Let’s get to know each other	<p>Priorities: familiarization, integration, establishing group cooperation rules, concluding a group contract, defining expectations, fostering openness, curiosity, and motivation to create.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Using the language of metaphors, we can say that creativity training is a journey into the realm of various possibilities within our minds. However, to start traveling together, you must get to know the crew well. The first meeting is an opportunity to get to know each other better and create a positive atmosphere for the upcoming trip. It is vital to establish the course of the joint journey and the conditions for free “drifting” in the right direction.</i></p>
Session 2: Better to ask the way than to go astray	<p>Priorities: stimulating curiosity, sensitivity to problems, developing questioning thinking, anticipating and making associations, and divergent thinking.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Curiosity and the experience of wonder are essential factors that foster creativity. The state of curiosity motivates us to ask questions and look for answers. It creates the need to notice problems, new interesting topics, and phenomena. Curiosity can lead to the discovery of new things and the need to improve what already exists. Experiencing wonder is rooted in the potential to embrace various viewpoints concerning an unexplored, undiscovered aspect of everyday life. This session aims to stimulate critical thinking, which in turn fosters openness, interest, and exploration.</i></p>
Session 3: Artistic inspirations	<p>Priorities: developing creative verbal and artistic expression, stimulating divergent thinking and creative imagination, transforming, developing aesthetic sensitivity, active reception of artists’ works, and the principle of deferred valuation of one’s products.</p> <hr/> <p><i>You don’t have to be an artist to create, but the workshop of many masters can inspire your creative endeavors. Diversity nourishes creativity and art, and its history at the turn of the century is a perfect example. The colorfulness of art – its trends, techniques, aesthetic revolutions, and the artists’ originality – can be a starting point for individual searches. Discovering the world and its creation can be combined with communing with works of art</i></p>

	<p><i>that express the worldviews of other artists. This confrontation fosters the formation of sensitivity as well as respect for individuality. During the classes, we will look at the world through the eyes of representatives of surrealism or suprematism, we will become the creators of street art, we will face lettering and typography, we will find ourselves in the studio of the painter Arcimboldi, and we will reflect on what hides behind the mysterious smile of the famous Mona Lisa.</i></p>
Session 4: The Time Machine	<p>Priorities: developing divergent thinking and imagination, stimulating curiosity, developing the ability to anticipate, create combinations, and stimulate interest in the past.</p> <p><i>The eternal dream of people is the ability to travel in time. The longer humanity and the Earth last, the more questions arise about the past and the future. More than one daredevil attempted to outwit time and transcend its limitations. It would be fascinating to experience posterity, which has hitherto been unknown to us. How did people live? What was the world like? Why are some events remembered and others forgotten? These and many other questions prompt us to search over many historical epochs. So let's prepare for the expedition into the fascinating corners of time. Let's move our imagination and reach where others have not. However, before this happens, we will first play the role of architects and constructors who will create an unusual machine – a time machine.</i></p>
Session 5: Time travel	<p>Priorities: making associations, abstracting, combining time travel with stimulating curiosity and openness to new experiences, and searching for universal, timeless content and values.</p> <p>Time travel enables us to travel to various stages of cultural development and the ingenuity of people. Traversing different historical spaces is not the goal of the class, but it is a rich and colorful background for generating creative thoughts. Historical epochs provide a context for designing creative situations. Both the times of Neanderthals, Egyptian mummies, mythological deities, medieval kings, pirates, and corsairs, as well as the era of geographical explorers, are interesting topics for many creative explorations.</p>
Session 6: Nature is the mother of ingenuity	<p>Priorities: abstraction, making associations, metaphorizing, transforming, observing, and an interest in natural phenomena (paying attention to using them for solutions in other areas of life).</p> <p><i>For centuries, Mother Nature has provided us with inspiration for solutions in various fields of science, everyday life, and aesthetics. Observing nature and its rich phenomena has often served to inspire innovative ideas, as exemplified by the design of a helicopter or crane. Emphasizing its significant role in inventiveness should help build respect for nature, especially as industrialization, civilization development, and the pace of these changes accelerate. Let's look for unusual things in the shape of clouds, look at fractals, find analogies between natural phenomena related to the Earth and our everyday life, and think about what trees would say to the world if they had the opportunity to speak.</i></p>
Session 7: On the trail of inventors and explorers	<p>Priorities: recognizing the role of innovation and invention in developing civilization, transforming, creating combinations, stimulating curiosity, and the need for experimentation.</p> <p><i>Many outstanding explorers and inventors who have significantly influenced the development of civilization have left their mark on the pages of history. As the great inventor and author of over 1,000 patents, Thomas A. Edison said: "To invent something, all you need is a little imagination and a pile of scrap metal." Was Edison right? Can anyone become an explorer or inventor? What qualities are conducive to becoming an inventor? And how can the pursuit of discoveries be stimulated? We will try to find answers to these and other questions during the class "On the trail of inventors and explorers". We will be faced with creating new and useful improvements to our lives.</i></p>
Session 8: Play on words	<p>Priorities: developing linguistic creativity, divergent thinking and imagination, stimulating verbal expression, creating combinations, and transforming.</p> <p><i>The creative use of language primarily manifests itself in the production of new words, sentences, and statements, as well as in adapting statements to the situation and the recipient's properties. Language games and activities are designed to enhance the participants' creative mastery of the language and stimulate their individual abilities. The regular use of language by humans is innovative. It has a potentially unlimited scope, according to "the father of modern linguistics," Noam Chomsky. Participants will learn about</i></p>

	<i>it by creating, among other things, anagrams, deciphering acronyms, generating solutions for Scrabble based on neologisms, creating "Taboo" playing cards, or inventing new rules of language.</i>
Session 9: Barrier breaker	<p>Priorities: breaking cognitive, physical, and psychosocial barriers, perceiving different points of view, developing divergent thinking, and transforming.</p> <p><i>An individual who wants to develop and discover new opportunities and face new challenges should be able to overcome the limitations that often appear on their way. Both mental and personality factors, as well as psychosocial factors such as stereotypes, functional fixation, or groupthink syndrome, can hinder the creative process and limit the full realization of individual potential. Training in breaking barriers and seeing the world and oneself from different perspectives leads to a change in the approach to problems and tasks, thus allowing you to acquire practical competencies needed in many areas of life.</i></p>
Session 10: A trip around the world	<p>Priorities: stimulating imagination and divergent thinking, developing openness to experiences, and curiosity.</p> <p><i>It isn't easy to imagine an education that ignores multiculturalism in the modern world. Exploring the world with its cultural, religious, and ethnic diversity fosters openness to otherness and to people, as well as to new experiences. On the one hand, it teaches us to notice individuality; on the other, to create what is typical. By observing and experiencing the diversity of cultures from many corners of the globe and the people living in them, the image of the child's world is broadened, and its accessibility is brought closer. Participants can embark on a trip around the world, where they discover, for example, specific traditions, customs, and cultural achievements of various nationalities, providing the background for developing their ideas. We will start our journey by greeting the Inuit in Alaska and see, among other things, the art of the country of the rising sun. We will also compare Poland to China, create musical instruments for the indigenous people of Australia, and in the Caribbean, we will turn into treasure hunters. Maybe we can decipher a mysterious letter in a bottle found on the shore of the Atlantic Ocean.</i></p>
Session 11: In the world of media and advertising	<p>Priorities include developing divergent thinking, imagination, and creative expression, as well as fostering self-awareness.</p> <p><i>The world of advertising and media is an area of human activity where creativity is paramount. Participants will become acquainted with some of the tools used by advertising creators and media professionals. Tasks requiring creativity, which are set before students, include slogans such as advertising, billboards, logos, TV shows, copywriting, websites, newspaper editorial offices, and announcement offices, serving as stimuli to implement their ideas and express themselves.</i></p>
Session 12: Field game	<p>Priorities: taking stock of the cycle of classes, developing coping skills, divergent thinking, stimulating curiosity and openness, and developing cooperation.</p> <p><i>The adventure with creativity training has come to an end. The field game organized in the forest is intended not only to develop creative tasks and problem-solving skills but also to promote and learn group cooperation. In addition to stimulating curiosity and the need for sensations, the meeting summarizes previous experiences. There are no winners – the prize is the children's creative activity and enjoyment during the forest crossing.</i></p>

The training was carried out as a series of extracurricular classes. The structure of each class was similar, consisting of four phases: creative warm-up, exploring the topic, a challenge (homework), and the presentation of outcomes. A common element of the entire series of workshops was fictionalization: a narrative built around a single topic and thematically tailored exercises designed to stimulate mental operations relevant to creativity, yet related to the

introduced topic. The story initiated by the trainer gave coherence to the entire course of the classes. The purpose of the *challenges* (participants' activities outside the classroom) was to maintain continuity in the learning process. These challenges served as a preview of the topic for the following classes, and the participants on the group forum shared their outcomes. An essential training principle was providing feedback on the creative process (see de Chantal et al., 2024). The portfolio method was used to collect participants' products systematically. Each participant had the opportunity to monitor their own work and thus observe the changes that were taking place. The program aimed to balance the forms of task implementation, ranging from group to team, dyad, or individual (Korde & Paulus, 2017).

Notably, the training curriculum was deliberately designed so that the training exercises did not directly reflect the posttest criteria. This approach aimed to avoid using tasks analogous to those in the test, thereby minimizing the risk of sensitizing participants to the assessment format.

Recognizing that the trainer also plays an essential role in the effectiveness of training (Glerum et al., 2021), considerable attention was given to the selection of trainers. Trainers conducting creativity training had professional knowledge in stimulating creative abilities and several years of experience in advanced creativity training. There were 15 trainers, 14 women and one man, all aged 23 to 25. The trainers were graduate students majoring in psychopedagogy of creativity (see Karwowski et al., 2007; Lebuda et al., 2013).

Missing Values and Data Analysis

Overall, fully completed data (pretest and posttest) were obtained from 530 participants out of 674 participants (79% of the total sample), but Little's (Little, 1988) missing completely at random (MCAR) test confirmed that missing values were missing completely at random ($\chi^2 = 8.87$, $df = 13$, $p = .783$). Therefore, we conducted our analyses twice: once using available data and once using full information maximum likelihood estimation (FIML). Both resulted in the same patterns; therefore, we report the results using listwise deletion, with a comment regarding FIML results when appropriate.

Our focal analyses involved two steps. First, we used two mixed 2x2 ANOVAs (2 [group] x 2 [time: pretest vs. posttest]) to examine if there were changes in creative potential and confidence attributable to creativity training. Our second analysis involved two mediation models. In Model A, we investigated whether training affects participants' creative potential, which in turn influences their creative confidence. Therefore, this model involved a mediational mechanism hypothesized by the CBAA. The mediator was a change in creative abilities; we obtained this change by including creative potential (CP) T2 results as a mediator while controlling for CP T1 results. The dependent variable was a change in creative confidence (CC), obtained using CC T2 as a dependent variable while simultaneously controlling for CC T1 (Hayes, 2015). Model B tested whether differences in CC caused by training are responsible for changes in CP, following the same logic as Model A. These two steps were repeated using FIML estimation: instead of mixed ANOVA, we relied on a multilevel model that controlled for participants' clustering in pretest-posttest measurements using the lmer package in R (Bates et al., 2015), while mediation models were tested using lavaan (Rosseel, 2012).

All analyses were conducted either in JASP (JASP Team, 2024) or R (R Core Team, 2023). Data and scripts are available in the Open Science Framework (OSF) repository:

https://osf.io/ryj6x/?view_only=4ac6f3a8be9641a19a565e46d2ffe858.

Results

In the case of CP (see the left panel in Figure 3), we obtained a significant effect of Group: $F(1, 574) = 211.89, p < .001, \omega^2 = .155$, Time: $F(1, 574) = 301.736, p < .001, \omega^2 = .098$, and—most importantly—*Group x Time* interaction, $F(1, 574) = 333.102, p < .001, \omega^2 = .107$. In the pretest, the control group obtained significantly lower scores in CP ($p < .001$, Cohen's $d = 0.39$), but this difference in favor of the intervention group was more than four times larger in the posttest ($p < .001, d = 1.77$). There was no change in the control group between T1 and T2 ($p = .527$), but a significant and considerable improvement was observed in the intervention group ($p < .001, d = 1.35$) (all comparisons were made with Holm correction for multiple tests).

When CC was considered (see the right panel in Figure 3), we found no main effect of Group: $F(1, 599) = 2.35, p = .126$, but significant effect of Time: $F(1, 599) = 9.250, p = .002, \omega^2 = .003$, and significant interaction *Group x Time*: $F(1, 599) = 31.152, p < .001, \omega^2 < .011$. Posthoc tests (with Holm correction) demonstrated that while the intervention and control groups did not differ in T1 ($p = .391$), they did in T2 ($p < .001, d = 0.33$). There was also a significant increase between T1 and T2 in the intervention group ($p < .001, \text{Cohen's } d = 0.34$) and a decline tendency—albeit insignificant—between T1 and T2 in the control group ($p = .176$).

Figure 3. Changes in CP and CC as a result of creativity training

A central and final set of our analyses consisted of two mediation models exploring the mechanisms of change in CP and CC thanks to the intervention and the role played by the change in CP for the shift in CC (ASCE) and—vice versa—the role of change in CC for a change in CP. A summary of both mediation models is provided in Figure 4.

As illustrated in the case of the CBAA-driven model (ASCE), taking part in the creativity training resulted in the improvement of creative potential (the effect on CP_{T2} controlling for CP_{T1} was estimated at $d = 1.08$), which consequently drove the improvement of CC (the effect on ΔCC : CC_{T2} controlled for CC_{T1} was significant, $\beta = .22, p < .001$). Overall, it resulted in a significant indirect effect “intervention- ΔCP - ΔCC ” of $b = 0.233$ [95% CI: 0.106, 0.361] (partially standardized indirect effect,

confidence intervals obtained with 5000 bootstrap samples). Notably, the change in creative potential (ΔCP) fully mediated the change in creative confidence (ΔCC), i.e., previously observed improvement of CC thanks to training can be entirely attributed to the shift in CP and the indirect effect was responsible for more than the two-third (66.8%) of the total effect. This pattern aligns with CBAA predictions and ASCE.

An alternative model, “intervention- ΔCC - ΔCP ,” also resulted in a statistically significant indirect effect. However, this effect accounted for only a negligible portion of the total effect of the intervention on creativity training (indirect effect = 4.2% of the total effect). Even after controlling for changes in CC, a large and significant direct effect of the intervention on CP remained ($d = 1.04$). Therefore, although changes in self-perception may be beneficial for changes in abilities, this indirect effect is far smaller than that of the alternative, CBAA-driven ASCE model.²

Figure 4. A Summary of Mediation Models Tested (CP = Creative Potential; CC = Creative Confidence)

Model A: The *Abilities-Shape-Confidence-Effect* (CBAA-driven model)

² These models were replicated using lavaan with FIML estimation. For Model A (ASCE), we observed a statistically significant “a path,” i.e., intervention- ΔCP : $b = 18.538$, $SE = 0.963$, $p < .001$ (an equivalent of Cohen’s $d = 1.082$) and “b path,” i.e., ΔCP - ΔCC : $b = 0.010$, $SE = 0.003$, $p < .001$ as well as statistically significant indirect effect (obtained with 1000 bootstrap samples) intervention- ΔCP - ΔCC : $b = 0.182$, $SE = 0.051$, $p < .001$ and total effect: intervention- ΔCC , $b = 0.298$, $SE = 0.059$, $p < .001$ (an equivalent of Cohen’s $d = 0.224$). At the same time direct effect intervention- ΔCC was not significant: $b = 0.116$, $SE = 0.080$, $p = .148$, thus showing full mediation. For Model B (To-Believe-Is-To-Rise-Effect), we observed a statistically significant “a path”: intervention- ΔCC , $b = 0.298$, $SE = 0.057$, $p < .001$ (an equivalent of $d = 0.366$) and “b path”: ΔCC - ΔCP , $b = 2.422$, $SE = 0.653$, $p < .037$ (an equivalent of $\beta = .115$), as well as significant indirect effect, $b = 0.723$, $SE = 0.234$, $p = .002$, total effect ($b = 18.538$, $SE = 0.985$, $p < .001$, Cohen’s $d = 1.082$), and direct effect intervention- ΔCP : $b = 17.816$, $SE = 0.997$, $p < .001$ (Cohen’s $d = 1.039$).

Model B: The To-Believe-Is-To-Rise-Effect

Note. Indirect effects are presented in partially standardized forms. d = Cohen's d . *** p < .001

Discussion

Creativity Training Develops Creative Abilities and Confidence

In this article, we focused on the effectiveness of an extensive and complex creativity training program for children and adolescents. This training proved highly effective in improving participants'

test scores and, albeit to a lesser extent, building their creative confidence. Overall, the effect size of changes in creative thinking exceeded Cohen's $d = 1$, indicating that participants' scores substantially improved after the intervention, surpassing both the pretest measurement and the control group. Given that the training program intentionally avoided training-to-test (see Table 1 for a description), the improvement in participants' creative abilities can be considered quite notable compared to the average effect sizes reported in previous meta-analyses (e.g., Scott et al., 2004a) and the usually applied benchmarks (Cohen, 2013; Gignac & Szodorai, 2016).

The changes in participants' creative confidence, although statistically significant and showing more favorable self-perception in the training group, were much more modest ($d = 0.35$) (cf. Meinel et al., 2019). These weaker effects may be caused by various reasons, three of which seem particularly relevant. The first is our single-item measurement, which may have been affected by a restricted range, thereby limiting our ability to accurately estimate the true effect. Second, the training itself focused much more on participants' cognition rather than their agency or motivation. Hence, the observed changes in confidence may be considered a byproduct of this particular training curriculum, strongly oriented toward cognition. Third and finally, improvement in confidence should not be taken for granted and assumed too easily. As demonstrated elsewhere (de Chantal et al., 2025), confidence may diminish when creative abilities develop, as people become aware that they have previously overestimated their potential. Hence, the metacognitive calibration process might be more complex, and a decline in confidence might actually denote better metacognition.

The Hypothetical Metacognitive and Agentic Mechanisms

Apart from examining the effectiveness of training, we were interested in exploring the mechanisms behind the observed changes in participants' creative abilities and confidence. One hypothesized mechanism assumed that the improvement in confidence is caused by changes in abilities resulting from training – the *Abilities-Shape-Confidence-Effect*. An alternative model examined whether changes in abilities occur due to changes in confidence: the *To-Believe-Is-To-Rise-Effect*.

The ASCE was a specific prediction derived from the CBAA model (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019), which posits that creative abilities drive creative confidence, which in turn enhances the likelihood of creative activity and achievement (see Lebuda et al., 2021). Previously, this proposition was only tested using correlational and longitudinal designs (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). The possibility of examining it experimentally was both needed and tempting, even if the current step is only the initial one and requires replication.

Still, the possibility that people improve because they believe in (or become aware of) their creativity seems likely, given recent theorizing in the creativity literature (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023; Urban & Urban, 2025), particularly the growing interest in creative metacognition. Considering individual differences, indeed, more metacognitively aware individuals are also more creatively skilled (Karwowski et al., 2020; Silvia, 2008; Urban & Urban, 2023). However, taking a more processual perspective, it remains unclear whether creative metacognition and growing confidence also contribute to changes in creative abilities or performance (see Zielińska & Karwowski, in press).

Given the design of our training study, we tested both these lines of reasoning using mediation models, where the change in creative potential (or the change in creative confidence) was regressed on group assignment (control versus intervention) and a hypothetical mediator (either the change in potential or in abilities). These doubly dynamic mediation models (see e.g., Groyecka et al., 2020, for a similar approach) should not be considered definitive, as—despite advantages—they suffer from an obvious limitation: both mediators and dependent variables were measured concurrently. Still, these models should be considered a first step toward more appropriate and dynamic tests that allow stronger causal conclusions about the links between creative potential and confidence.

The mediation models provided results indicating that both hypothesized effects might be at play. First and foremost, the improvement of participants' creative confidence was fully mediated by the change in their creative potential. This effect suggests that metacognitive mechanisms are at play: participants in the intervention group were mostly accurate; they self-perceived themselves as

more creative, and their abilities had indeed improved. This pattern aligns with the CBAA predictions that creative abilities might shape creative confidence, even if strong causal claims are still premature given the limitations of this design.

An alternative model provided less systematic, yet still interesting effects. We observed that changes in creative confidence were associated with a slight yet significant improvement in creative abilities. Thus, although training itself was highly effective in boosting participants' creative skills, part of this effect can be attributed to the very fact that people became more confident of their creativity, or—to put it differently—more aware of their skills. Therefore, although we acknowledge that, above all, the improvement in creative potential was mainly due to the intensive and diversified exercises provided in the training, there was still a significant confidence-driven effect. Those who improved their confidence as a result of participation in the training tended to benefit in terms of their creative abilities as well.

Educational Consequences

Those results and their theoretical consequences might inform educational practice and future research. Since creativity training is typically a group-based form of learning (Reiter-Palmon & Paulus, 2019), it is essential to consider the social nature of metacognitive regulation. Solving problems in small training subgroups creates an opportunity for metacognitive experiences that may trigger socially shared metacognition (Iiskala et al., 2011). Moreover, collective confidence fosters learning, encouraging group members to demonstrate and/or assert their abilities and knowledge to others (Aggarwal et al., 2023). Observing co-participants who successfully confront challenges can not only strengthen creative performance but also boost others' confidence (cf. Groenendijk et al., 2013).

Creative education programs, including the training presented in this article, might strengthen participants' creative confidence by engaging them in activities that mobilize internal resources necessary to meet the requirements of tasks or situations. Mastery experiences can trigger young people to perceive themselves as active subjects of their own creative lives, a critical factor in

adolescent identity formation (Barbot & Heuser, 2017). Conceivably, during creativity training, a feedback loop exists between mastery experiences related to perceived self-development and an increase in belief in the possibility of achieving specific creative goals, as creative confidence stimulates motivation and effort. Consequently, well-designed training can mitigate the risks of creative mortification and allow the growth of creative aspirations (Beghetto & Dilley, 2016).

There is broad agreement that creativity can be developed in various ways, both through extended, intensive, and in-depth training and short-term interventions (Haase et al., 2023). Although the former is usually more effective, it requires more effort, time, space, and is more costly. The results of brief training or wise interventions are promising, and their popularity has been increasing in recent years (Haase, 2023; Zielińska et al., 2022b). Still, there is a need to develop novel training approaches with an explicit metacognitive focus akin to wise interventions (Karwowski et al., 2022; Zielińska et al., 2022b).

Strengths and Limitations

This study boasts unique strengths, the primary being the extensive (and effective) creativity training program, which is described in detail elsewhere (Wiśniewska, 2021), allowing us to go beyond simple pretest-posttest comparisons and test some more sophisticated hypotheses discussed in this article. There are, however, also limitations that should be taken into consideration when interpreting our findings. We see at least four of them as being particularly important.

The most apparent limitation relates to our single-item measure of creative confidence. Although similar items have been used previously in the literature (see Kaufman, 2019), we recognize that the limited variability of participants' responses may have influenced the effect size obtained and the ability to correctly estimate the true effect size of changes in confidence. Therefore, future studies using both more elaborate and dynamic, as well as task-related measures of creative confidence (Karwowski et al., 2018; Zielińska et al., 2022a), are necessary to replicate and extend our findings.

The next point—and a second limitation—relates to a sort of methodological (measurement) and “substantial” asymmetry³ of our study. “Methodological asymmetry” denotes that, compared to elaborate, performance-based measurement of creative ability, the measurement of confidence (single item) in our research was very straightforward. Better (i.e., more valid, reliable, but also diversified) measurement naturally allows for stronger conclusions and higher sensitivity. Consequently, a much stronger effect size for changes in creative potential than confidence might be, at least partially, associated with the way the focal constructs were measured. This limitation aligns with the “substantial asymmetry”. Indeed, the primary goal of the training presented in this paper was not to strengthen participants’ creative confidence or other agentic aspects of their functioning, but to enhance their creative thinking. Therefore, different effect sizes obtained for changes in creative potential and confidence—while expected—have consequences for our ability to properly test hypothesized mechanisms. In short, if the overall effect of change is tiny (as was the case with confidence), it makes it harder to mediate other effects due to limited variability. This limitation naturally calls against strong causal claims and implies the necessity of “more symmetrical” designs and measurements.

The third limitation is the lack of perfect randomization of participants between intervention and control groups, illustrated by statistically significant differences in creative potential in the pretest. Participation in the training was voluntary, so the students recruited to the intervention group were likely more motivated to participate in pretest and posttest measurements. Self-selection bias may indeed be a factor contributing to the very high overall effectiveness of the training. On the other hand, however, given the length and intensity of the training, it seemed hardly feasible to convince participants to take part if they were not interested in the training in the first place. Moreover, even if our training participants were highly motivated from the outset, they still improved substantially as a result of the training.

³ We thank the anonymous reviewer for highlighting this point.

The fourth apparent limitation is the character of the creativity tests used, both being primarily figural. Given the dominance of verbal divergent thinking tests in the creativity literature (Long et al., 2022; Snyder et al., 2019), it is interesting to investigate whether the observed effects replicate when creative abilities involving other modalities are assessed. This is another line of future research stemming from this investigation.

Future Directions

The study presented in this paper calls for replication and addressing the limitations of the current design. While some of the next steps seem quite obvious – e.g., a more elaborate measurement of creative confidence, adding verbal creativity tests, or utilizing training programs that place equal emphasis on cognitive and agentic aspects of creativity – there are also other research directions worth considering. We discuss four of them with the hope of inspiring future research.

The first research direction that seems vital to undertake touches the mechanisms through which creativity training works. In this paper, we posited that such mechanisms might be metacognitive and agentic; however, our suggestion is not exhaustive. Motivation and effort, cognitive strategies learned, utilizing feedback, benefiting from co-creation, and other factors may contribute to an individual's improvement in training. Usually, the training itself (and its curriculum) is considered the only independent variable that causes the changes in participants' scores. Yet, how exactly does this change occur? More dynamic processes and designs, preferably with multiple measurements instead of pretest-posttest only, are necessary to answer this question.

The second direction relates to the mechanisms we focused on in this study, particularly the ASCE. Suppose people's confidence develops as a result of their abilities, as the CBAA model (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019) posits. How can we test this prediction without conducting a training study? Manipulating abilities or any other individual differences is tough, given they are—by definition—relatively stable. What can be manipulated, however, is people's performance in tasks measuring creative potential, e.g., divergent thinking tasks, which are usually used as a proxy for

creative abilities. It is well-known that people generate more creative ideas when they are explicitly asked to do so (the “be creative” instruction, see Harrington, 1975; Wei et al., 2024). Does this effect translate into their higher confidence, i.e., are those asked to be creative indeed more creative, and does this boosted performance predict their higher confidence? Such a scenario could serve as an independent examination of the ASCE effect.

A related line of inquiry extends the focus of the current study into other sources of creative confidence and agentic self-perception. We know that success brings confidence, yet the opposite is not always true (Sitzmann & Yeo, 2013; Talsma et al., 2018). Therefore, future studies, especially those based on intensive measurements and interventions, are needed to more definitively answer the question of whether feeling creatively confident increases the likelihood of creative behavior, whether the opposite is true, or both effects co-occur. Both more recent examinations (Zielińska & Karwowski, in press), as well as previous studies (Vancouver et al., 2002) and meta-analyses (Sitzmann & Yeo, 2013) show that, especially at the within-person level, the situation might be more complex and the causal link when confidence strengthens behaviors or creative successes should not be taken for granted (see also Beghetto & Karwowski, in press, for a discussion).

The final line of potential future inquiries worth considering takes a more developmental orientation. Creative abilities change with age (Jankowska & Karwowski, 2025; Said-Metwaly et al., 2021), and the same applies to metacognition (Schneider, 2008) and creative self-beliefs, including creative confidence (Karwowski, 2015b; Karwowski & Barbot, 2016). Therefore, the question of whether the effects tested in this study are moderated by participants’ age is indeed an interesting one.⁴ Indeed, the strength or even existence of some of the mechanisms can be qualified by age

⁴ We appreciate this suggestion of an anonymous reviewer. Although it was beyond the scope of our study, we examined whether our mediation models and each of the paths tested are moderated by participants’ age. We used Hayes’ (2015) model 59, with age moderating all paths in both models, i.e., a path (“intervention-mediator”), b path (“mediator-DV”), and c’ path (“intervention-DV”). Except for including a moderator, both models were specified precisely in the same way as presented in the Results section.

For a model with ΔCP as the dependent variable, age did not moderate the “a path” ($b = -0.033$; $SE = 0.027$; $p = .234$), indicating that the effect of the intervention on change in creative confidence did not differ between participants of different ages. There was no age-moderated “b path” ($b = -0.345$, $SE = 0.252$, $p = .169$); hence, the change in creative confidence translated into a change in creative potential similarly across age groups. There was, however, a statistically significant age-moderated c’ path (“intervention- ΔCP ”), $b =$

cohorts, with younger participants probably relying less on their self-beliefs and metacognition than adolescents or adults. This, however, is to be tested.

Conclusion

Creativity training not only develops creative potential but can also build students' agentic feelings – their creative confidence. Moreover, this study provides empirical evidence that the growth in creative potential, thanks to creativity training, is responsible for the increase in participants' creative confidence. Overall, creativity training may have metacognitive benefits, as it not only enhances participants' creative potential but also increases their awareness of this improvement. Moreover, these findings are well-aligned with one of the critical propositions of the CBAA model: that creative potential influences creative confidence.

0.898, $SE = 0.414$; $p = .031$, indicating that the intervention had stronger effects on creative potential among older participants than among younger ones. Still, while the effects differed by age, the training was effective even among the youngest participants. Notably, however, for testing the “to-believe-is-to-rise” effect, the conditional indirect effects: “intervention- ΔCC - ΔCP ”, was significant and strong among younger participants (11 y.o.), $b = 1.158$, $SE = 0.419$, 95% CI : 0.428, 2.070, weaker yet significant among slightly older participants (13 y.o.), $b = 0.743$, $SE = 0.242$, 95% CI : 0.306, 1.265, and insignificant among oldest participants (16 y.o.), $b = 0.291$, $SE = 0.229$, 95% CI : -0.107 , 0.800. Thus, it seems that the “to-believe-is-to-rise” effect was not observed among older participants, who benefited from training for reasons other than a change in their confidence.

For a model with ΔCC as the dependent variable, there was no moderation effect of age on the “a path”, $b = 0.725$, $SE = 0.413$, $p = .08$ (“intervention- ΔCP ”), or “b path” (“ ΔCP - ΔCC ”), $b = -0.054$, $SE = 0.036$, $p = .125$, or “c’ path” (“intervention- ΔCC ”), $b = 0.001$, $SE = 0.001$, $p = .523$. Conditional indirect effects were virtually the same and statistically significant across all age groups. Thus, it appears that the ASCE was robust, regardless of participants' age.

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